

Enhancing Patient Satisfaction by Redesigning OPD Slip in Ophthalmology: A Quality Improvement Project

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Abstract

Objective: This quality improvement project evaluated the impact of redesigning the Outpatient Department (OPD) slip in the Ophthalmology Department of Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar, on patient and physician satisfaction, consultation efficiency, and service quality.

Methods: The study was conducted in two phases. In Phase I (January 2022), 100 adult patients completed a structured Urdu version of the PSQ-18 questionnaire to assess baseline satisfaction. The OPD slip was then redesigned to include patient demographics, medical history, examination findings, and treatment advice. After one month of implementation, Phase II (May 2022) surveyed another 100 patients and five ophthalmologists. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25 with descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results: Post-intervention, 95% of patients reported easier access to consultants, and 99% noted improved signage. Satisfaction regarding examination duration and the clarity of written instructions increased from 67% to 87% and from 44% to 92%, respectively. Physicians reported 100% satisfaction with documentation completeness and 98% with overall quality of care. Waiting time, however, remained unchanged.

Conclusion: Redesigning the OPD slip substantially improved patient and physician satisfaction, documentation accuracy, and consultation efficiency, demonstrating that minor administrative modifications can enhance the quality of outpatient healthcare services.

Keywords: patient satisfaction, outpatient department, quality improvement, ophthalmology, healthcare communication, service efficiency.

JEL Classification: I11, I12, I18, L15, M31

1. Introduction

Healthcare is evolving to meet the rising demands for quality and patient-centered care Biresaw et al. (2021); Iftikhar et al. (2025). Enhancement of the patient experience has become a major objective of healthcare reform. Patient satisfaction is among the most significant service performance measures. It indicates the patient reviews about the care processes, communication, accessibility, and interpersonal elements of healthcare provision Ferreira et al. (2023); Qureshi et al. (2025); Iftikhar et al. (2023). Patient satisfaction is not limited to an emotional reaction, but it is a quantifiable measure of service quality. Research demonstrates that satisfaction among patients increases the likelihood of adhering to medical recommendations, continuing to trust health professionals, and getting improved health results Kruk et al. (2018); Hussain et al. (2024); Alshanbari et al. (2023). Consequently, patient satisfaction has become a significant contributor to healthcare performance which results better clinical outcomes.

The Outpatient Department (OPD) is the first point at which patients meet the healthcare system, most of the time Sharma et al. (2025). Patient satisfaction is a vital measure of healthcare quality and a significant determinant of patient compliance and trust Naidu (2009). Administrative design components, such as the OPD slip, play an important role in shaping the patient experience in outpatient departments, particularly in ophthalmology, where repeat visits and coordination of diagnosis are standard Fiebach et al. (2007). Studies consistently show that patient satisfaction in an outpatient setting depends on several factors. They include waiting time, registration efficiency, communication between doctors and patients, physical comfort, and administrative coordination Waters et al. (2016). Research in both developing and non-developing countries has consistently emphasized that although patients appreciate the technical competence and polite behaviour of clinicians, information flow is inefficient and there is administrative dissatisfaction. Biresaw et al. (2021) conducted a study that among the factors that affect patient satisfaction, staff communication and waiting time were significantly important compared to the perceived medical expertise of physicians. Mohd

and Chakravarty (2014) has shown that the negative impact of delays in consultation, lack of instructions, and wrong documentation systems had an adverse effect on patients even in high-quality facilities. Sanjeewa and Senevirathne (2017) also noted that inadequate explanation of treatment plans, overcrowding, and lack of proper queuing systems were the major reasons that contributed to dissatisfaction in outpatients in Sri Lanka.

Similar trends are observed in Pakistan, where overcrowding and resource constraints tend to reduce the delivery of patient-centred services Rahman et al. (2019). Ullah et al. (2025) study that 57.5 % of patients visiting the teaching hospitals in Peshawar gave high ratings on outpatient services. It further reported that poor communication and long waiting times decreased satisfaction. In Karachi, a cross-sectional analysis found that 51% of respondents considered OPD services satisfactory, but there were still significant gaps in their administration. Hussain et al. (2019) ensured that even though the aspects of service quality had a positive correlation with satisfaction, waiting time was an extremely frustrating factor. These papers confirm that the issue of administrative inefficiency can damage the perception of patients even with the high level of medical competence.

One of the most important factors in regard to outpatient satisfaction is clinical documentation. The OPD slip is an administrative document of the simplest and significant nature. It links registration, clinical examination, and the follow-up of care Lal et al. (2020). It includes simple data, such as the patient's name, presenting complaint, diagnosis, and physician instructions. Nevertheless, the designs of OPD slips are not ideal in most hospitals. They might not have systematic areas to record medical history, examination results, or a guide for follow-ups Sahay and Walsham (2017). This results in poor documentation, breakdown in communication, and inefficiency in the consultations. In the event of missing crucial data, doctors must repeat questions, prolonging the consultation and increasing frustration for both patients and staff. Evidence provided by ophthalmic services highlights the need for proper documentation. Missing or disorganized data may result in diagnostic delays or misunderstanding of the treatment. Shah and Khan (2004) discovered that in low-vision clinics in Peshawar, patients rated provider competence and were less satisfied with documentation and clarity of the communication. Similarly, Afsar et al. (2024) observed that written instructions were found to have enhanced satisfaction when they were easy to follow. Enhancement of documentation is thus an easy yet effective quality improvement initiative. Properly arranged OPD slips enable a smooth workflow, proper record-keeping, and effective communication. It helps doctors remember crucial information, allows patients to understand instructions easily, and supports continuity of care between visits. These reforms are low-cost but capable of producing considerable results in terms of satisfaction and clinical outcomes Mukhtar et al. (2013).

The OPD slip is used to transmit necessary information, prescribed medications, and follow-up instructions to patients. The uncertainty in the design of the OPD slip can create a range of barriers to communication, leading to misunderstandings, missed appointments, or medication errors ???. Although multiple studies have examined factors that influence outpatient satisfaction (communication, waiting time, and administrative processes), few have evaluated simple administrative tools, such as the OPD slip, as targeted quality-improvement interventions in high-volume ophthalmology settings Khattak et al. (2012). A clear, structured OPD slip can reduce information gaps, improve written instructions, and streamline consultations, but evidence from tertiary public hospitals in Pakistan is limited. This study therefore aimed to evaluate whether a redesigned OPD slip would improve (1) patient navigation and satisfaction, (2) the completeness and usability of clinical documentation, and (3) consultation efficiency in the Ophthalmology OPD at Hayatabad Medical Complex. We hypothesized that structuring the OPD slip would increase patient and physician satisfaction and reduce consultation time, without necessarily affecting registration waiting time. To determine the satisfaction level of patients attending the eye OPD at Hayatabad Medical Complex before and after designing the OPD Slip.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Study Design

This was a two-phase, before-and-after quality improvement project conducted in the Ophthalmology OPD at Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar. Phase I (baseline) was conducted from January 1 to 30, 2022, and Phase II (post-intervention) from May 1 to 30, 2022.

2.2 Study Setting

The research was conducted in the Outpatient Department (OPD) of the Ophthalmology Unit at Hayatabad Medical Complex (HMC), a large tertiary care medical facility in Peshawar. The hospital serves a large population of both urban and rural patients in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province. The OPD operates six days a week and provides non-urgent ambulatory services to more than 200 patients daily. By the time the study was conducted, the department used manually captured OPD slips for each patient visit.

2.3 Study Population

The target population consists of adult patients (aged 18 years or older) visiting the Ophthalmology OPD for non-emergency eye care services during the study. Patients under 18 years of age, those with emergency conditions, and individuals receiving priority treatment (e.g., hospital staff, armed forces personnel) were excluded to minimize bias arising from preferential service delivery. Furthermore, five ophthalmologists working in the OPD were included in Phase II to evaluate satisfaction and usability from the provider perspective.

2.4 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Adult outpatients (≥ 18 years) presenting for non-urgent care were recruited by convenience sampling; patients under 18 years, emergency cases, and those receiving priority service (hospital staff, armed forces) were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

2.5 Study Instrument

Patient satisfaction was assessed using the PSQ-18 questionnaire, translated into Urdu and back-translated to ensure accuracy. The instrument assessed access, communication, time spent, and clarity of written instructions; responses were collected on a 5-point Likert scale. The OPD slip was redesigned to include structured fields for patient demographics, chief complaint, past medical history, medication list, comorbid conditions, key ophthalmic examination findings (visual acuity, slit lamp/lamp observations, retinoscopy notes), diagnosis, and clear written treatment/follow-up advice. The redesign also included the treating consultant's name to assist navigation.

Phase I: Baseline Assessment In the first phase, 100 patients were selected from the period of 1st Jan 2022 to 30th Jan 2022, who were prepared to be discharged from the OPD, were recruited. The study was not conducted in patients under 18 years of age or those who received priority (e.g., staff of the hospital and armed forces). Data collection was conducted with informed written consent and an interviewer-administered questionnaire. Three investigators were trained in data collection.

Health care service patient satisfaction was measured using the Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire Short Form (PSQ-18), a validated English-language scale. The questionnaire was converted to Urdu, and finally it was translated again by another individual. The questionnaire is subdivided into four sections that are used to determine the socio-demographic status of the patient, their access to the health care services, waiting time as well as the level of satisfaction with the available physical facilities, services offered by the staff, information provided and overall satisfaction with the provided full service, available physical facilities, and staff. The aspect of satisfaction with each item was measured using a 5-point scale, which included strongly satisfied, satisfied, unsure, dissatisfied, and strongly dissatisfied.

Redesigning the OPD Slip: The OPD slip was redesigned to include structured fields for patient demographics, chief complaint, past medical history, medication list, comorbid conditions, key ophthalmic examination findings (visual acuity, slit-lamp observations, retinoscopy notes), diagnosis, and clear written treatment or follow-up advice. The redesign also included the treating consultant's name to assist navigation. Figure 1 shows the comparison of the old and newly designed OPD slips. After implementing the necessary changes, the design was shared with the hospital management for official use.

Phase II: Post-intervention Evaluation: After a month of successful implementation and use of the new OPD slips, the second part of the data collection began on 1st May, 2022, and ended on 30th May, 2022. The second phase was selected, in which 100 patients and five ophthalmologists were chosen. Patient satisfaction and waiting time for their appointments and examinations were measured. Doctors' satisfaction levels were also measured regarding their experience with the redesigned OPD slip, which included all baseline information.

Figure 1: Comparison of the old and newly designed OPD slips.

Figure 2: Patient satisfaction before and after Redesign the OPD slips

2.6 Data Collection and Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed in SPSS version 25. Continuous variables were summarized using mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Between-phase comparisons used chi-square tests for categorical variables and independent t-tests for continuous variables; results were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Five ophthalmologists provided feedback on provider satisfaction and usability in Phase II.

3. Results

The study involved 200 patients, with 100 enrolled at each stage. During the pre-intervention period (Phase I) 54 only of the participants were males and 46 only were females, among post-intervention period (Phase II) 63 only of the participants were male and 37 only were females. Phase I participants had a mean age of 49.7 \pm 8.1 years (between 18 and 67), whereas that of Phase II was 45.5 \pm 10.1 years (between 18 and 64). During the two phases, the majority of the respondents were of the 36-50 years range and had attained the intermediate levels of education or higher. Most of them belonged to the lower-middle socioeconomic classes and lived in urban areas. The similarity between these demographics suggests that the two groups were comparable, and the difference in outcomes after the intervention can be attributed to the redesigned OPD slip rather than to demographic differences. Table 1 provides the demographic information of patients at both stages. In the first phase of the project, some basic and essential questions regarding convenience in finding the concerned OPD, the concerned doctor, and a proper signage system were asked of patients. The response of patient navigation and signage is displayed in Table 2. After the completion of the first phase of data collection, some administrative changes were made, including adding the name of the concerned doctor to the OPD slip and installing more signage, symbols, and arrows in the OPD to improve patient understanding. The differences in patient satisfaction before and after redesigning the OPD slips are displayed in Figure 2. There was significant improvement in perceived accessibility and ease of navigation in the outpatient department among patients. 82% of patients said they could easily access the ophthalmology OPD upon registration, and 85% said the same after redesign. The

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of patients

Details	Phase I	Phase II
Age		
18-35	23	20
36-50	40	39
51 and above	37	41
Education Level		
Primary	4	7
Secondary	9	12
Intermediate	43	37
Bachelor	31	40
Higher Education	13	4
Socioeconomic Status		
Lower Class	25	18
Lower Middle	43	49
Upper Middle	19	23
Higher	13	10
Marital Status		
Married	76	72
Unmarried	24	28
Residency		
Urban	57	61
Rural	43	39
Occupation		
Unemployed	5	7
Government employed	30	29
Non-government	38	47
Labor	17	10
Student	10	7

Table 2: Patient navigation and signage responses

Question	Response	Phase I	Phase II
Is it easy to access the Appropriate OPD after getting the OPD slip?	Yes	82	85
	No	18	15
Is it easy to find a consultant of your choice in OPD after getting a slip?	Yes	37	95
	No	63	5
Is the signage, symbol, and arrows in OPD appropriate?	Yes	19	99
	No	81	1

rating for selecting the consultant of choice was higher in Phase II at 95% after the consultant name was included in the new slip, compared to Phase I at 37%. Also, the proportion of satisfaction with signage, symbols, and directional arrows increased to 99% compared to 19% by following the implementation of standard visual indicators throughout the department. Such results show that, through straightforward administrative interventions such as labeling and standardizing signage, the experience of accessibility for patients can be significantly improved.

Table 3 compares the patient care satisfaction between Phase I and Phase 2. There was also an improvement in patient satisfaction with the doctor-patient interaction following the implementation of the redesigned slip. The percentage of patients who described their experience of studying the examination as mostly satisfactory departed from 67% to 87%. Phase I rated the doctor and Phase II rated 72 and 99% of respondents, respectively, as having a satisfactory level of knowledge about the medical history and current state of the patients. Similarly, there was a small increase in comfort level when discussing medical issues, from 90% to 93%. The largest positive change was seen in the level of clear, understandable written instructions or treatment advice, which rose to 92% after the redesign, compared with 44% before. Furthermore, the rate of satisfaction with the completeness of examination increased to 89-59 %, and the satisfaction with the time the doctor spent at the consultation grew to 75-50 %. These results show that the new OPD slip helped establish a more efficient and organized consultation process, allowing physicians to access the necessary clinical information faster

Figure 3: Doctors' feedback on documentation completeness after OPD slip redesign.

and share treatment instructions with greater clarity. The positive effects of the intervention were

Table 3: Patient care and communication satisfaction

Patient Care Item	Response	Phase I	Phase II
Overall experience during the doctor's examination	Satisfactory	67	87
	Unsatisfactory	33	13
The doctor adequately understood your medical history and current condition during the examination	Satisfactory	72	99
	Unsatisfactory	28	1
Feel comfortable discussing your medical concerns with the doctor	Satisfactory	90	93
	Unsatisfactory	10	7
Instructions or advice given by the doctor regarding your condition and treatment are well-written and understandable	Satisfactory	44	92
	Unsatisfactory	56	8
The examination process was thorough enough to address your health concerns	Satisfactory	59	89
	Unsatisfactory	41	11
Time the doctor spent with you during the examination	Satisfactory	50	75
	Unsatisfactory	50	25

also assessed through ophthalmologists' feedback. The corresponding participation of the five doctors (100%) expressed satisfaction with the redesigned OPD slip. The results suggest that redesigning the OPD slip significantly improved the completeness of patient information and reduced the need to ask repetitive questions. They reported that the structured layout facilitated more accurate recording of comorbidities, medication history, and investigative results, which ultimately improved patient care quality. The doctors reported that the general quality of documentation improved from 80% to 98% without the intervention and after the intervention, respectively. The doctors also reported easier patient flow and better utilization of consultation time, which reflect the practical value of the redesigned format. The satisfaction of doctors after the redesign of the OPD slip is categorized in Figure 3. Table 4 illustrates the patient response regarding the waiting time. Regarding time-related indicators, the intervention had both positive and negative effects. The average time required to obtain an OPD slip during registration did not differ significantly between the two phases. During both stages, approximately one-half of the patients had their slip back in 5 to 15 minutes, approximately one-third in 15 to 30 minutes, and less than one-fifth in more than 30 minutes. This implies that the redesign of clinical slips did not directly affect registration efficiency, as this process occurs before patient examination. However, examination time also improved significantly. The percentage of patients that were analyzed within five minutes increase to 50 %, whereas those who took over half an hour to receive care dropped to 3 %. The general satisfaction with the length of examination had increased to 80% as compared to 49%, showing that the restructured slip enabled faster and better-organized examination.

Table 4: Comparison of waiting and examination times between Phase-I and Phase-II

Category	Time	Phase I	Phase II
Time taken for OPD slip	Less than 5 min	6	5
	5–15 min	45	40
	15–30 min	33	35
	More than 30 min	16	19
Time taken for examination	Less than 5 min	16	50
	5–15 min	54	43
	15–30 min	9	4
	More than 30 min	21	3

Figure 4: Effect of waiting and examination time on patients' satisfaction level

Figure 4 gives the waiting time effect on patients' satisfaction level. We find that patient satisfaction influences waiting time concerning the examination time, going up to 80% from 49% of the OPD Slip redesign, because this enables the consultant to accelerate the process and recall each baseline with great information, but tremendous levels of dissatisfaction (nearly 70%) with acquiring OPD slips.

4. Discussion

This quality improvement project demonstrated that a simple redesign of the OPD slip significantly improved patient navigation, clarity of written instructions, thoroughness of examinations, and completeness of physician-reported documentation in a high-volume tertiary ophthalmology clinic. These improvements were observed within one month of implementation and were apparent across multiple patient-reported domains. The results clearly show that the structure and content of the OPD slip significantly improved patient and provider experiences. Records of communication and documentation were found to be the most noticeable. Once the redesigned slip was implemented, understanding of doctor-written recommendations and treatment instructions improved significantly, according to patient reports. A standardized format of documentation helped to reduce the issue of ambiguity and helped to understand the information, as the necessary data, like medical history, medications, and examination findings, were systematically recorded. Spatial allocation and clear formatting also enhanced doctor-patient communication, leading to higher overall satisfaction. The updated format also increased physician satisfaction, as the enhanced design enabled quick access to relevant data and easier documentation. As a result, unnecessary duplications were minimized, time was saved, and vital aspects of the examination were accurately recorded. Subsequent consultations were hence more focused and fruitful, as seen through patient satisfaction. Moreover, the culture of clinical communication and continuity of care was improved, which enhances accurate patient monitoring and follow-up.

The accessibility and navigation for patients in the outpatient department were also improved through the intervention. By attaching the name of the consultant on the appointment slip, and increasing the amount of signage and directional signs, helped the patient to locate their physicians and also provided a more positive experience of the outpatient process. These steps were therefore helpful in achieving a more efficient and smoother outpatient encounter. Our findings are consistent with the earlier study that suggested the administrative and communicative improvements have a significant effect on patient satisfaction Bhati et al. (2023). As opposed to interventions like digitalization, which were resource-intensive, our economic redesign achieved significant effect sizes in signage/navigation and clarity of written instructions, which corresponds to the existing evidence that clear written communication enhances patient observance and satisfaction. The magnitude of improvement in signage and ability to locate the consultant (from 37% to 95%) is notable and suggests that small operational changes can yield outsized benefits in patient experience. The patients indicated that the assigned service areas enhanced their awareness of efficiency and coordination of care. Although there was a marked increase in communication and consultation processes because of the redesigned slip. No significant reduction was observed in the waiting period before receiving the OPD slip. Consistent with our finding Nelson et al. (2014), the administrative workload and staff levels are more likely to contribute to registration delays than the design of documentation. Thus, the further increase of this aspect will involve more operational reforms, including the increase in registration counters or the electronic system. In the current research context about healthcare services, 67% report the average satisfactory time during examinations with doctors in 1st phase, which grows to 87% post-intervention. 92% report being satisfied with the comprehensibility of any instruction/advice written by the doctor about their condition/treatment. After redesigning the OPD slip, the doctors' satisfaction rate on completeness of patient information and significant

history is enhanced to 100%, which improves the quality of patient care in these aspects to 98%. A satisfactory change (49% to 80%) was observed in examination time during phase II. But there was no change or improvement observed in the waiting time to obtain an OPD slip. The research demonstrates that a relatively low-level administrative intervention can result in significant changes in the level of healthcare as demonstrated by Rozenblum et al. (2013). The reformed OPD slip not only improved patient satisfaction but also enabled doctors to have complete and accurate information in their documentation. The redesigned OPD slip lowers the risk of information gaps, continuity of the provided care, and enhancement of the overall service delivery. It is also helpful in clinical governance since medical records are standardized and easier to access. The findings of the current research indicate that patient satisfaction is not mainly linked to clinical competence; the design and efficiency of administrative processes also have an impact. The effective experience with this evidence-based intervention demonstrates that complex quality-improvement programs should be integrated into hospitals' everyday routines. The action plan used was the assessment of current processes, gaps identification, specific changes, and evaluation; the model can be applied in other departments to improve service delivery.

5. Conclusion

This paper shows that a systematic OPD slip redesign can bring significant changes to clinical processes and patient experience in a tertiary ophthalmology environment. The intervention resulted in increased patient contentment with communications, navigation systems, and documentation, and increased completeness of physician records, without requiring any substantial financial or infrastructural expenditure. Clinically, the redesigned slip facilitated the exchange of information between patients and doctors, improved the recording of examination findings, and ensured continuity of care by providing clear advice. The efficiency and patient satisfaction outcomes obtained highlight the potential of simple administrative tools to improve the quality of care and patient safety in resource-restrained settings. From a data science perspective, the organized fields that have been included in the new slip provide a platform of systematic data capture and digital integration. With such standardized documentation, it is possible to support the creation of electronic health records, facilitate regular quality-improvement audits, and generate analyzable datasets for health services research. At a more general level of policymaking, this low-cost, evidence-based intervention provides a model that can be scaled by other high-volume outpatient departments in Pakistan and other healthcare systems. The integration with hospital information systems in the future may allow automating the data entry, providing the ability to monitor the data in real-time and predictive analytics to optimize the services. Overall, the OPD slip redesign is a viable, sustainable approach to enhancing patient satisfaction, clinical documentation, and readiness for data, thereby bridging the gap between the everyday clinical routine and the present-day data-driven healthcare.

LIMITATION AND FUTURE WORK

This study used convenience sampling and was conducted in a single tertiary public hospital, which may limit the generalizability of findings. The short interval between implementation and evaluation limits inferences about long-term sustainability. We relied on self-reported satisfaction measures and a small number of physician respondents ($n=5$). Additionally, we did not measure clinical outcomes or patient adherence, which could be considered in future work. Future studies should evaluate the long-term sustainability of the redesigned slip, explore electronic integration of OPD slips, examine the effects on clinical outcomes and follow-up adherence, and address registration workflows to reduce wait times.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed equally to the conception, design, analysis, and writing of this study. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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